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Creolization: an autobiographical journey around a concept

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Abstract

Stumbling across the concept of creolization was a matter of chance discovery and, for most of my academic life, intermittent engagement. I noticed it first as a student at the University of the Witwatersrand, next when travelling to West Africa, then subsequently when I met students with Caribbean roots at the University of Birmingham. Switching to the study of migration and spending two years as at the University of the West Indies in Trinidad also influenced me. My sporadic travels to Mauritius provided key insights into Indian Ocean creolization. After reading the work of two Scandinavian scholars I concluded that finding out how, why, when and where creolization manifested itself was a crucial way of understanding how social difference could be surmounted. Fortunately, the award of a professorial fellowship to study the historical and comparative manifestations of creolization enabled me to start (but sadly not finish) this long quest.

Keywords

Early life and apartheid; Creole linguistics; Creoles in Sierra Leone; Creolization Caribbean; Creolization Indian Ocean; generalizing creolization

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Introduction

I grew up in a white suburb in Johannesburg, South Africa, at the height of the apartheid regime. Locked in a narrow world of friends, family and the local primary school, it took me an inordinately long time to realise that ‘something was off’. What was ‘off’, of course, was that I had no friends, teammates or schoolmates who were not white, while my parents mainly socialized with family, neighbours or *landsleit* (people of the same geographical origin), in their case Lithuanian or Polish Jews.

My social world was suddenly and massively enlarged by going to the University of the Witwatersrand (Wits). It was the early 1960s and the apartheid government had just legislated to segregate the universities by racial categories but students of all backgrounds who were already registered were allowed to continue their degrees. Fortunately, student protesters and sympathetic administrators and academics ensured that Wits never became entirely white. I became life-long friends with two Indian South Africans and was also close to a few black students. I plunged increasingly into an unfamiliar set of social spaces – teaching night school to black workers, enjoying what were daringly described as ‘multi-racial parties’, grooving on ‘township jazz’ and engaging in earnest conversations with a gay couple of indeterminate ethnic origins.

Valkhoff and the creolization of the Cape

It was probably my sense of an expanding world that induced me to go to a few of Marius François Valkhoff’s lectures on linguistics, even though I was not registered for his course. I knew absolutely nothing about him, other than that he was the Professor of French Studies. I was puzzled why he was lecturing on Portuguese and Creole. (At that time, 1963 or 1964, the word ‘Creole’ was totally unfamiliar to me.) I have only recently discovered how extraordinary Valkhoff’s talents were. Born in the Netherlands, he acquired near fluency in nearly all the Romance languages – Italian, French, Portuguese and Romanian – while, in addition to being a distinguished linguist, he was interested in parapsychology and theology (Noordegraaf 2006). However, it was his expertise in Portuguese and Creole languages that is salient here.

Valkhoff’s lectures resulted in a book titled *Studies in Portuguese and Creole with special reference to South Africa* (1966). The book appears at first sight to be narrow and scholarly, but it nonetheless caused a political controversy in South Africa, and his lectures provided a revelation to me. To understand why, some background is needed. As Perry Anderson (1962a; 1962b) has clarified, the Portuguese empire was a bit of a shambles compared with the other European empires. It was extensive and profitable, but Portugal never had the population or capital to effectively settle, penetrate and militarily dominate its territories. Instead, it relied mainly on trading outposts serviced by well-crafted carracks and galleons, and on the diffusion of the Portuguese language, often resulting in pidginization and creolization. (Pidgins are simplified contact languages, while Creoles are deeper merged languages, which become mother tongues.) Very broadly, as Valkhoff contended, Portuguese was the global language of the seventeenth century, French the global language of the eighteenth century, with English taking over from the nineteenth century until the present.

Given this background, Valkhoff argued that it was not at all surprising that Portuguese Creole was widely spoken at the Cape in the seventeenth century. Cape Town was a trading post par excellence and had turned, Valkhoff (1966, 161) declared, into a ‘most colourful and cosmopolitan little town’. While the ships calling at the Cape were mainly Dutch, the seafarers came from many places. The population included retired colonials from the Far East, local Khoi (then known pejoratively as ‘Hottentots’), slaves (in 1658 there were 198 slaves compared with 166 whites), freed slaves and many of mixed racial origins. The language of the small number of Dutch settlers, later to become Afrikaans, was creolized, that is infused with the languages, including Portuguese Creole, spoken by these different populations (Valkhoff 1966, 161–2).

Although much of his book deploys the language of technical linguistics, there are strong indications that Valkhoff knew that he was stirring up a hornet’s nest in drawing attention to the mixed social and linguistic heritage of the Afrikaner people. He is quite explicit that it is misguided to trace Afrikaans solely to Middle Dutch, Flemish, Dutch and Low German dialects. It is a ‘diachronic’ and ‘albo-centric’ error, to focus on a single genealogy of the language and privilege its European constituents (Valkhoff 1966, 192 *et seq.*). What he discerned was that for the internal logic of apartheid to make sense, there also had to be a pretence that ‘pure’ white Afrikaners were speaking an essentially pure European language. By demonstrating and documenting that Afrikaans was creolized, Valkhoff was subverting the ideology of apartheid in an unexpected, and somewhat cunning, way.

Much later, as I continued my study of history and politics, I became more and more convinced that by paying insufficient attention to the concept of creolization I had thrown away a vital tool in understanding and contesting apartheid and racism at its very roots. My fellow students and I were much more focused on inequalities driven by class and believed that framing political issues in racial categories was both erroneous and somehow playing the apartheid government’s game. I was attracted instead by Nkrumah’s Pan-Africanism and the potential for labour movements to organize African workers and drive progressive social change on the continent.

An unexpected encounter with Creoles in Sierra Leone

I left South Africa in 1964, aged 20, a few days after my final undergraduate examinations and within a few years found myself a master’s student at the London School of Economics, a doctoral student at the Centre for West African Studies at the University of Birmingham and a Commonwealth Scholar at the University of Ibadan, Nigeria. In line with my Marxian proclivities, my PhD thesis was on the Nigerian labour movement, later published as *Labour and politics in Nigeria* (Cohen 1974/2024).

I had married Selina Molteno in London in 1967, just before we sailed to Nigeria where she worked at the Institute of African Studies at the University of Ibadan, while I pursued my fieldwork and lectured in political science. Our adventures in Nigeria during that country’s civil war are recounted in our joint memoir (Molteno & Cohen 2020), but before we reached our destination I experienced another chance encounter with Creoles (this time with Creole people, rather than Creole languages).

In travelling to Nigeria, we were on the last voyage of an Elder Dempster passenger liner, one that had faithfully plied the route between Liverpool and West Africa for many years, stopping at a number of the Anglophone ports along the way. When we reached Freetown, we breathed in the hot, humid West African air with some apprehension and leaned over the rails with intense curiosity. We were treated to a hilarious skit by dock workers who enacted the last rites of the British empire, barking out incomprehensible orders, marching with wooden rifles and hauling down the British flag. Even more compelling was a group of about 40 attractively dressed, demure women and courteous, suited men

nearly all wearing hats and engaging in subdued conversation while walking *up* the gangplank. Our visitors were Sierra Leonean Creoles who had booked high tea on board for as long as the ship was in port to commemorate the last time they would see the SS Apapa.

Years later I found a second-hand copy of a gem of a book, Arthur T. Porter's *Creoledom: a study of the development of Freetown society* (1963), which explained who these fascinating figures were. A Sierra Leone Creole himself, he combined insider knowledge of the community with commendable historical rigour and a plentiful injection of sociological imagination. As Porter (1963, 10–11) explained, the Sierra Leonean Creoles we observed were the descendants of four different groups:

- First, during the period 1787–1791 about 400 'Black Poor', sixty 'nondescript' white women and 119 'white persons' in and around London were shipped to the colony. (The expression 'nondescript' is pretty certainly a euphemism for sex workers.)
- Second, 1,192 'Black Loyalists' from Nova Scotia, who had supported the British cause in the American Revolutionary War, chose to come to Sierra Leone in 1792. These 'Nova Scotians' had been slaves mainly in Virginia and South Carolina and were freed in exchange for serving in the British army. While some stayed in Canada, and others were shipped to Tobago and London, those who came to Sierra Leone formed a core component of Creole society.
- Third, about 600 Jamaican Maroons arrived in 1800. Maroons were escaped slaves who created rural redoubts in the Jamaican mountains and fiercely fought any attempt to re-enslave them. They were tricked into surrendering, then shipped to Nova Scotia before being given free passage to Freetown in Sierra Leone.
- Finally, about 99,000 'recaptives' (Porter simply says 'a vast number') were landed in Freetown by the Royal Navy in the period 1807–1857 following the British abolition of the slave trade. 'Recaptives' were captured Africans on ships intercepted by the Navy before they had crossed the Atlantic. A court of the Vice-Admiralty in Freetown 'released' these putative slaves and most chose to stay in Sierra Leone.

It was from these four diverse elements that a new Creole population emerged. They had little enough in common other than being beneficiaries or victims of the British empire and all either spoke or had encountered the English language. That was sufficient to fashion an English-based Creole language, known as Krio, spoken eventually as a lingua franca by nearly all the colony's population. Sierra Leonean Creoles were based in Freetown and dominated its political, intellectual and social life. One, Sir Henry Lightfoot Boston (1898–1969) became the Governor, others were distinguished musicians and intellectuals. They ran businesses, occupied professional roles and were strongly represented in the priesthood and colonial bureaucracy.

Figure 1. Bishop Samuel Crowther was a recaptive born in Nigeria and a stalwart member of the Creole community in Sierra Leone. Anglicized and Christianized, he became the Bishop of West Africa and translated the Bible into Yoruba.

Creoles did not, however, constitute the majority of the population of the colony and as nationalist sentiment grew after the Second World War political power shifted to representatives of the Temne and Mende, the largest indigenous ethnic groups. The Creoles we had seen onboard our ship in 1967 were still members of a social elite but, like the British empire with which their fate was closely entangled, their power was on the wane. As they slowly became more marginal, many migrated to Britain, the USA, Canada and other parts of West Africa.

I did not pursue my passing interest in Creoles at the time, but I now had a number of the pieces of the puzzle lodged in the recesses of my mind. This was as far as I had reached then. Creoles could be languages or people or both. (I later established Creole people could be phenotypically very different – white, black or many shades in-between.) Creolization involved the fusion of different elements into new cultures and identities, and it seemed that this process happened as a result of empire, migration and some kind of historical conflict, possibly of a traumatic sort.

Birmingham and the Caribbean connection

There the matter lay for a few years. I spent 1969–1977 at the University of Birmingham pursuing my research and teaching on comparative labour movements and the sociology of development. As was only to be expected, offering a course on development attracted a mix of students from all over the world, but a notable cohort had Caribbean origins and connections. For reasons that need not detain us here, Caribbean Studies was barely represented in British universities at the time and those who wanted to find an echo of their roots came to listen to what I had learnt of West Africa and to share what they knew both of the Caribbean and of their lives in the UK. As often happens in these encounters, the teacher became the student, and I was gradually sucked into the intriguing world of the Caribbean archipelago, where Selina and I, plus our two children, were to spend two happy years (1977–9).

The students I encountered at Birmingham included Ivan Henry, Paul Gilroy, Fitzroy Ambursley, Philip Nanton, Melanie Thompson, Dexter Hutt and Clive Harris (and, later, Winston James) all of whom have made notable contributions in academia and in other fields.¹ I was also friendly with the cultural theorist, Stuart Hall, who is justly lionized for his pathbreaking contributions. Although born in Jamaica, Stuart Hall wrote relatively little about the Caribbean, in marked contrast to his English-born wife, Catherine Hall, who make outstanding contributions to Caribbean history. (I should, however, note that Stuart Hall fronted a seven-part television series on the region, *Redemption Song*, transmitted in 1991.)

As I have mentioned Stuart Hall here, I will break with the strict sequence of my autobiographical journey to deal with his formative essay on creolization, centred on the Caribbean, titled '*Creolité* and the process of creolization' (Hall 2010/2003). While it has been reproduced several times in different collections (including one of my own) and widely cited, Hall can be questioned on a few points. He uses *creolité* essentially as a translation of creolization and insufficiently addresses its provenance, first as a counter-argument to Aimé Césaire's *négritude* and second as a normative literary movement anchoring the expressive and performative arts of the French Caribbean (Bernabé et al. 1989). Hall also implies that Édouard Glissant's views align with the theorists of *creolité* whereas Glissant distances himself from some of their arguments.²

Where Hall's article remains invaluable is in his idea that creolization in the Caribbean is a complex and evolving composite of three 'presences' – *présence africaine, présence européenne and présence américaine* (Hall 2010: 30). While insightful, we can add the *présence asiatique* (East Indian and Chinese) as well as the smaller numbers from the Ottoman Levant. Given his Caribbean origins, it was natural that his examples focused on the Caribbean. However, the heritage components of creolization vary geographically – for example, there was no *présence américaine* in Cape Verde (the fount of creolization) or the Indian Ocean, while the American heritage was vestigial in the case of West Africa. Ignoring these minor correctives, Hall is 'spot on' in pointing to a crucial property of the concept of creolization, namely that mixture emphatically does not imply equality. As Hall (2010, 29) puts it:

The colonized refashions the colonizer to some degree, even as the former is forced to take the imprint of the latter's cultural hegemony. This does not mean that in Creole societies cultural elements combine on the basis of equality. Creolization *always* entails inequality, hierarchization, issues of domination and subalternity, mastery and servitude, control and resistance. Questions of *power*, as well as *entanglement*, are always at stake.

In making this key argument, Hall has certainly been influenced by Edward Kamau Braithwaite, whom he cites and whose major work *The development of Creole society in Jamaica* (1971) made a powerful impact. The book was important in challenging the prevailing 'pluralist' thesis that stressed the segmentation between the classes and races in the Caribbean. By contrast, Braithwaite argued that whites, 'free people of colour' (that is those of mixed ethnic heritage) and black slaves were all creolized in terms of their adopted and adapted customs, institutions, religions and patterns of family life. In language, sexual liaisons and social encounters, creolization knitted elements of the society together, though in a complex, uneven and incomplete way.

I will not linger further on the Caribbean in this article, other than to say that, curiously, our residence there did not add greatly to my theoretical repertoire. Our two-year stay in Trinidad was more of a lived experience of creolization than a result of 'beating books' (as my students at the University of the West Indies called reading and studying). Our children participated in Carnival and adopted local accents and idioms. We were friendly with 'Trinis' of many ethnic and religious

backgrounds and kept remarking to each other how Trinidad represented a counter-model to the apartheid South Africa of our youth. Of course, there was racial awareness and much friendly banter about social differences, but ethnic conflict was rare.³ We frequently used the services of an Indo-Trinidadian taxi driver who proclaimed he was a Hindu but took the precaution of draping his car mirror with a St. Christopher pendant. He also arranged to have his car sprinkled with holy water at a nearby nunnery, courtesy of the friendly Catholic sisters. These measures encouraged him to drive with an amiable but terrifying recklessness.

Creolization in the Indian Ocean

I first became aware of the extent of creolization in the Indian Ocean when I was given an unexpected opportunity – to give advice on how to organize and regulate the emerging Faculty of Social Sciences at the University of Mauritius. No doubt this assignment had deeper roots in the UK Colonial Development and Welfare Act passed at the end of the Second World War, but thirty years later it had survived in the ‘big sister’ relationship the University of Birmingham’s enjoyed with the University of Mauritius (founded in 1965). The Inter-University Council for Higher Education Overseas brokered the arrangement. I was provided with an allowance to buy a tropical suit (really!) and flown to the island for a two-month tour of duty. Between meetings and drafting faculty regulations I explored most bits of the island and soon realized that my very limited French was not understood – most of the islanders spoke Kreol Morisien. The language was French-based and was not at all dislodged by the occupation of the island by the British from 1810.

On this and follow-up trips, I became friendly with a remarkable couple, Ram Seegobin and Lindsey Collen. Ram is a UK-trained doctor while Lindsey, who was born in South Africa, has thrown herself so firmly into Mauritian life that her six novels are set on the island and several are published in Kreol Morisien, a first. They live in a deliberately modest style in a village called Bambous where Ram practices ‘barefoot medicine’, offered free or at modest cost to his neighbours. Both, but particularly Lindsey, are significant figures in Lalit de Klas (‘Class Struggle’), a political party with ideological roots in Marxism, anti-colonialism, environmentalism and feminism. The party has survived for nearly half-a-century and has had a strong political impact, while failing to secure parliamentary representation. Saliently, the party campaigns in Kreol, while publishing its documents and manifestos in both English and Kreol. It draws support from all sections of Mauritian society, which is predominantly descended from India but also has many of mixed origins, notably those of African backgrounds (often signified by the label ‘Kreol’) together with small white and Chinese communities.

As one soon learns, in Mauritius ‘Kreol’ is both a minority ethnicity and a majority language. Beyond and interlacing these two features is an enveloping creolized culture, developed by those who settled on the island, or were brought there against their will from the seventeenth century onwards (Vaughan 2005). The blending of the constituent heritage cultures is seen, for example, in Kreol cuisine. Take *rougaille*, a spicy tomato-based sauce that is often paired with prawns, chicken, eggs and sausages, or *fish vindaye*, which combines South Asian pickles, marsala paste, garlic and shallots with chunks of fresh fish. In addition to savouring the wonderful Kreol food, visitors are often invited to beach parties where African, Malagasy and other traditions are celebrated in popular *sega* dances and songs.

Figure 2. The Ylang-ylang plantation in Mauritius sells essential oils at its Maison Créole. This is an impressive example of botanical and cultural borrowing – ylang-ylang is the Spanish spelling of the Filipino Tagalog term for the *Cananga odorata* tree, not native to the island. (Author’s photo, 2014)

Other, but somewhat similar, varieties of creolization are found in Réunion, the Seychelles and the Comoros and in even smaller islands. My wife and I were fortunate to observe creolization in Réunion at first-hand through the good offices of my doctoral student, Laurent Medea, together with his charming wife, Anaïs, and his family. Medea’s key publications in English (2002, 2010) provide vivid testimony to the difficulties of forging a distinct Creole identity in the face of a relentless push to integrate the island into all things French. Legally, Réunion is a *département et région d’outre-mer* (an overseas department and region) which is fully part of France, even though it is 9450 km from Paris. This confers many advantages to the islanders (for example, they are full French citizens and profit from regional aid), but this process of ‘departmentalization’ is also a challenge to those who wish to protect their identity and the vernacular language, Kréol Réyoné. As Medea argues (2002, 138):

On the cultural level, the [French] authorities wish to maintain their francophone links with Réunion as a means of broadening the influence of French culture. From a Réunionese point of view an assimilationist policy invokes two types of reaction: part of the assimilated population adopts French culture and become Francophile; the others militantly resist assimilation. ... In the next two generations it is anyone’s bet what will become of identity and departmentalisation.

My experiences in the Indian Ocean gave me another key insight into creolization. Creole languages, identities and cultures are frequently naturalized and habituated through a multiplicity of small interactions taking place over a long period. However, they are also under threat from majority and hegemonic cultures – advanced, for example, by Indo-Mauritian politicians or by the French state. Protecting and promoting creolization can thus become a political cause, one associated with defending the interests of a subordinate group and valorizing popular forms of expression and resistance, in short a *lalit de klas* (class struggle). This applies particularly to Creole languages, which are often held to be an inferior version of the lexifier despite the latter being less widely spoken. (A lexifier is the language spoken by a dominant group that provides the bulk of a Creole language’s vocabulary.) Thus, Cape Verdean Kriolu has a lower status than Portuguese, Kreol Morisien is trumped by French, Sierra Leonean Krio-speakers defer to English-speakers, and so on (Amado 2023).

Can creolization be generalized to become a global concept?

As the numbers of my direct and fleeting experiences of creolization multiplied, I slowly fixed on an idea that it would be an instructive and useful project to see whether creolization could be generalized to become a global concept with a complex, multi-faceted past and a significant theoretical future. This idea came to me at a challenging time in my academic career, around 2001–3. I had agreed to become Dean of the Faculty of Humanities at the University of Cape Town over this period, allowing Selina and me to reconnect with our place of birth after 36 years away and also an opportunity to make a positive contribution to the better post-apartheid future towards which we had worked. It was a wonderful and rewarding time, but the administrative workload was remorseless, and it was difficult to find enough leisure to think and write.

One puzzle that preoccupied me was to understand the implications and limitations of the idea that South Africa was, or could be, a ‘rainbow nation’ and how this differed from creolization. The notion of a rainbow nation was advanced by Desmond Tutu, then taken up and elaborated by Nelson Mandela, before being symbolized in the new South African flag and generalized as an optimistic vision of the post-apartheid order. Of course, this was an advance on apartheid, where fabricated ‘races’ were forcibly separated from one another, required to live in separate zones, attend racially-defined schools and forbidden to intermarry. The abolition of these provisions was liberating and created many new opportunities for those held back by the apartheid state.

These positive changes do not, however, mean that a rainbow nation is bound to morph into a Creole society. Voluntary segregation between phenotypically different groups remains persistent in restaurants, educational institutions and public spaces, though these are now open to all. Some 30 years after its invention it is only possible to shout out ‘two cheers for the rainbow nation’ though, of course, two cheers are far better than none at all.

Creolization – two Scandi professors and three Indian novelists

While I was in the early stages of thinking about the universality of the notion of creolization, others were ahead of the game. In particular, two exceptional Scandinavian scholars, whom I subsequently met and liked, had made important contributions. The first, Ulf Hannerz, was a prominent and prolific researcher on cultural complexity, but one of his articles with a striking title caught my attention. It was simply titled ‘The world in creolization’ (Hannerz 1987) and was principally a reflective musing about his fieldwork in Nigeria. It had become apparent to Hannerz that the culture he had observed was neither coherent nor homogenous. Anthropologists were still clinging to this outdated idea despite the fact that all cultures were shot through with external influences, mixture and movement. This led him to the view that ‘a concept of Creole culture with its congeners may be our most promising root metaphor’. He cites with approval Lee Drummond’s remark that ‘there are now no distinct cultures, only inter-systemically connected, creolizing cultures’ (Hannerz 1987, 550, 551). Although his direct analysis of creolization is quite limited, Hannerz clearly had in mind its universality, remarking in his conclusion that Creole cultures were not only to be found in colonial and post-colonial settings, but also appeared in his native setting, Sweden, a country that had not been colonized for the last half-millennium.

Perhaps significantly, a second major scholar of creolization, Thomas Hylland Eriksen, was also Scandinavian. With apparently limitless energy, he burst out from his small, relatively-homogenous, home country, Norway, to undertake research in many places, not least places that were familiar to me like Trinidad and Mauritius, before his untimely death in 2024. I think of Thomas with some emotion as he agreed to speak at a conference I organized despite his advancing terminal illness. He

had written a good deal about creolization and related topics, but my favourite remains his article on 'Creolization and creativity' (Eriksen 2003). He is full of praise for Ulf Hannerz's role in challenging traditional anthropology and covers a number of general themes before developing a suggestive trichotomy, describing three 'families' of identity – pure identities, hyphenated identities and Creole identities.

Each of Eriksen's families of identity carries dangers. Those espousing a pure identity can get trapped by fundamentalism and stagnation, leaving them unable to adjust to rapid change. Those in the family of hyphenated identities are somewhat better off, but they can become victims to inter-generational or intersubjective tensions between the past and the present. Although experiencing the dangers of the unfamiliar, somewhat akin to seafarers venturing into unknown waters, those with a Creole identity can adopt and adjust at the social and intersubjective level to the mixture and movement characteristic of a global age. The pressure to draw new maps and make new decisions feeds the creative impulse as individuals and wider social groups seek to overcome, adjust or embrace ambivalence. This propels a close connection between creolization and creativity. While cognitive linearity and social closure characterize old societies and heritage cultures, cognitive irregularity and social openness are consistent with current societies marked, as they are, with openness, complexity and indeterminacy (Eriksen 2003, 235).

As Eriksen notes, given the association between creativity and creolization it is not at all surprising to find that distinguished novelists like V. S. Naipaul and Salman Rushdie depict characters exhibiting Creole identities. Among their many works one might mention Naipaul's *A house for Mr Biswas* (1961) and Rushdie's *The Satanic verses* (1988). Eriksen (2003: 223) cites Rushdie's own comment on his book. For its author, *The satanic verses* 'rejoices in mongrelization and fears the absolutism of the Pure. Mélange, hotchpotch, a bit of this and a bit of that is how newness enters the world. It is the great possibility that mass migration gives the world, and I have tried to embrace it'. The publication of the book led to a fatwa by Ayatollah Khomeini, the Supreme Leader of Iran, who called for the death of Rushdie and his publishers in 1989. After avoiding several attempts on his life, in August 2022 Rushdie was a victim of a dreadful knife attack that left him blinded in one eye. Although the fatwa was framed in theological terms, it may usefully be interpreted as a fearsome struggle between a defensive pure identity and an emergent Creole identity.

To these two novelists, I will add a third – Amitav Ghosh. In his trilogy, *Sea of Poppies* (2008), *River of Smoke* (2011) and *Flood of Fire* (2015), Ghosh explores how pidginization and creolization arise when Indian indentured workers leave their homes to work on plantations in the Indian Ocean. Innovatively, he depicts how embryonic Creole cultures are fashioned on the sea crossing even before cohabitation in colonial settings. While of different generations, all three writers are members of the massive Indian diaspora, one that has interacted with many people in many lands – in Fiji, Natal (South Africa), Uganda, Trinidad, Guyana, Jamaica and St. Lucia and elsewhere during the period of empire and with the USA and the United Arab Emirates, Malaysia, Saudi Arabia, the UK, Canada, and Australia after 1948.

Conclusion: the voyage ahead

I returned from South Africa to my academic position at Warwick in the UK in 2004, finally with the intellectual tools, time and inclination to undertake a systematic and comparative study of creolization. Winning an Economic and Social Research Council professorial fellowship and relocating to Oxford gave me the opportunity to pursue my interest in depth. With the help of an able research assistant,

Paola Toninato, I worked on creolization in Brazil, Louisiana, Martinique, Dominica, Cape Verde and (again) on Mauritius. Later, as a byproduct of a Leverhulme programme on diasporas, my valued colleague, Olivia Sheringham, and I probed the connection between diasporization and creolization. The published results included an extensive reader (Cohen and Toninato 2010), a book (Cohen and Sheringham 2015), a special issue of a journal, about a dozen articles and chapters and some more ephemeral material. The funders pronounced themselves satisfied, but though I was content with the collaborative books, I never was happy with my own output and felt generally that my efforts lacked the impact I had hoped for and that the notion of creolization deserved.

I was up against it, to be sure. Concepts and near synonyms describing ethnically-mixed societies abound – from pluralism, interculturalism, multiculturalism and cohabitation to notions of transnationalism, conviviality, cosmopolitanism, diversity, and superdiversity.⁴ These concepts need proper exposition, and all have their virtues as well as drawbacks. Even closer to the concept of creolization was hybridity, notably developed by the prominent post-colonial literary theorist, Homi Bhabha (1994). As with creolization, Bhabha's version of hybridity, emphasized the creative energies and new meanings found in the 'the third space', where two cultures intersected. Again, echoing Hannerz's and Eriksen's accounts of creolization, Bhabha questioned the very idea of fixed cultures and identities.

At some moments, I was ready to throw the towel in. If so many of my friends and colleagues were adopting 'hybridity' to describe phenomena akin to creolization, why not go with the flow? I was particularly disheartened after an informal chat with Stuart Hall, who also understood the dilemma, but largely adopted Bhabha's vocabulary. My stubborn streak persisted. Hybridity is wrong on so many levels. It evokes biology not culture. While biologists recognize the possibility of heterosis (hybrid vigour), many hybrid plants are sterile, and even when fertile can produce poorer characteristics than the parent plants. This signals exactly the opposite of energetic and groundbreaking creativity. There is no credible account of inequality between cultures in hybridity theory whereas, to repeat Hall's comment quoted above, in creolization 'questions of power, as well as entanglement, are always at stake'.

Also important for me is that creolization, is both a recognized historical process and a lived reality. People have Creole ancestors and describe themselves as Creoles, not as 'Hybrids'. They speak Creole, not Hybrid. They create Creole music and cook Creole food, not Hybrid music and food, and so on. Moreover, this history and lived reality was predominantly located in the Global South and is spreading from there to other parts of the world. Similar processes located in the Global North had not acquired the label of creolization. Rather than automatically defaulting to ideas developed in the Global North, Is it not about time that our theories and vocabulary to describe such process are also drawn from the experiences and ideas of the Global South or, as one might more assertively put it, the Global Majority? This proposition is eloquently advanced by Gurinder Bhambra (2014).

It is not as if we are lacking in reputable scholarship and challenging theorists writing on creolization and related themes from outside Europe and non-North America. I have already cited Edward Brathwaite, Stuart Hall, Édouard Glissant Jean Bernabé (and his collaborators Patrick Chamoiseau and Rafaël Confiant), and can easily add Michel-Rolph Trouillot (1998) on the 'miracle' of creolization and Françoise Verges (2007) on creolization in the Indian Ocean. Key theorists from the Global South writing on cognate themes include Fernando Ortiz (1940) on transculturation, Aimé Césaire (1939) on *négritude*, Gilberto Freyre (1946) on Luso-tropicality and racial democracy and José Vasconcelos (1997) on the 'Cosmic Race', a 'fifth race' blending all cultures and civilizations in Latin America.

Younger scholars working on creolization include the Dominican historian Lennox Honychurch (2000), Shona Jackson (2012), Ananya Kabir (2020, 2022), Aisha Khan (2004), Viranjini Munasinghe (2006) and my former student at the University of the West Indies, Patricia Mohammed (2002). These scholars have extended creolization to other fields like dance and choreography as well as questioned whether East Indians in the Caribbean and indigenous people more generally are adequately served by historic accounts of creolization. Their views are usefully summarized by Islam (2023).

In short, there are credible accounts and lively debates about the extent to which the idea of creolization can be generalized beyond its historically-recognized heartlands.⁵ So I persist in my task. I want to give the last word to Raphaël Confiant, one of the Martinican authors of the powerful manifesto, translated as *In praise of creoleness* (Bernabé et al. 1989). In an interview with the news channel France 24 (2025) Confiant declared: '*Creolité* is not a mixture of genes, of chromosomes, although, yes, we are a mixed race as a result of history. But it is above all a result of mixture of cultures, traditions, imaginations and the desire to live together. And that's its strength. In fact, *creolité* is the opposite of apartheid'. And so, in my mind, I have come full circle and ended my journey. I now realise that my excursions were sometimes an explicit critique but were much more often a subliminal escape from the apartheid of my youth.

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Figure 1.2. Author's photograph.

Notes

- 1/ Ivan Henry gained his PhD, worked for the Commonwealth Youth Programme in Guyana and moved to Barbados. Paul Gilroy is a celebrated social theorist and author of *The black Atlantic* (1993). Winston James and Clive Harris collaborated on an important edited book *Inside Babylon: the Caribbean diaspora in Britain* (1993). Both stayed in academic life, Winston moving to California, while Clive holding posts at Warwick and Birmingham. Fitzroy Ambursley and I collaborated on an edited work, *Crisis in the Caribbean* (1983/2024). Dexter Hutt was knighted in 2004 for his outstanding work in improving Birmingham's schools. Melanie Thompson worked as an administrator in Birmingham while Philip Nanton, after a successful academic career in England, has had a luminous second flowering as a writer and performance poet in the Caribbean.
- 2/ A useful summary of his ideas is in Glissant (1998). His differences with the advocates of *creolité* are clarified by Collins (2017).
- 3/ The most important counter-example was a botched coup d'état mounted by a radical Muslim group, the Jamaat al Muslimeen, in July 1990. The group held hostages (including the prime minister) at the parliament building and the television station. Twenty-four people were killed, and many were injured before the insurgents were overpowered. This event was wholly anomalous. I should add that, although inter-ethnic violence barely exists, criminal and gang violence have become much more common since the mid-1980s.

- 4/ The idea of superdiversity was successfully advanced by my great friend and colleague, Steve Vertovec, who is at pains to point out that he was not only alluding to ethnic differences, but also that 'superdiversity' is multidimensional, referring to legal status, sexuality, language use, civic acceptance, age and other inequalities and differences (Vertovec 2023: 48–120).
- 5/ I acknowledge too that there are challenges to this generalizing project mounted by significant scholars.

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